

Studies on Interaction of Acid Bentonite with Aluminium Hydroxide Gel

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The nature of acidity of a freshly prepared colloidal H-bentonite and its changes on aging and interaction with aluminium hydroxide gel have been evaluated from electrometric titrations. Fresh H-bentonite shows two acid species H_2O^+ (57 me) and $Al(H_2O)_6^{3+}$ (22 me). On aging three acid species, H_2O^+ (23 me), $Al(H_2O)_6^{3+}$ (35 me) and hydroxy-Al polymers (21 me) are observed. Interaction of fresh H-clay with hydroxy-Al gel produces only one type of acidity (75 me). In X-ray diffraction pattern, the basal spacing of fresh H-bentonite 13.88 Å shifts to 15.36 Å (diffuse band) in gel treated H-clay mixture. On glycerol treatment 18.06 Å of H-bentonite shifts to 17.16 Å in gel treated H-clay mixture. In DTA curve dehydration peak temperature, 150°, of H-bentonite shifts to 130° in gel treated H-clay mixture. The dehydroxylation peak temperature 570°, of H-clay is lowered to 555° in gel treated mixture. Such differences are explained as due to fixation of hydroxy-aluminium in interlayer spaces in the unit cell structure of clay.

PREVIOUS studies¹⁻¹⁰ on acid clays have identified exchangeable H_2O^+ and $Al(H_2O)_6^{3+}$, $(AlOH)_2^+$ etc as active acid species which hydrolyse on aging with time to polymeric hydroxy-aluminium behaving as potential or latent acid species (Bronsted type). This investigation has been undertaken to understand the nature of titratable acidities of a fresh acid clay and of an aged acid clay and that of interaction product of acid clay with synthetic aluminium hydroxide gel.

Experimental

The clay material was $<2\mu$ fraction isolated from a bentonite sample (Rajasthan) by the usual method¹¹ of dispersion and sedimentation. H-bentonite was obtained by passing Ca-bentonite through a column of H-resin (IR-120, Amberlite). The structural formula of the clay mineral was obtained from the data on chemical analysis by standard methods¹².

One portion of the H-clay was immediately titrated with NaOH. Another portion was allowed to age for 4 weeks before subjecting it to titration with NaOH. The mixture of H-clay and $Al(OH)_3$ gel was prepared by mixing H-clay with that portion of $Al(OH)_3$ gel as being equivalent in terms of Al^{3+} to the amount released on aging the H-clay for 4 weeks. The mixture was allowed to age for 4 weeks before titration. The $Al(OH)_3$ gel was prepared by adding 0.1 N NaOH to requisite amount of $AlCl_3$ (AnalaR) and freed from NaCl. The pH of the prepared gel was 6.0. The temperature during experiment was maintained at $30^\circ \pm 0.5$. For titration* of these three systems 0.5% suspensions were taken separately and equilibrated for 24 h with

increasing amounts of 0.02 N NaOH. The pH and conductance were measured after equilibration. The results are shown in Fig. 1.

The X-ray analyses¹³ of air-dried clay samples were done on Philips model 1010 (Cu target, Ni filter) with 11.54 cm Debye-Scherrer camera. Lattice spacings and intensities of the lines are given in Table 1.

Differential thermal analyses¹⁴ of air-dried fresh and aged bentonite samples and of the clay-gel mixture are shown graphically in Fig. 2.

Results and Discussion

The chemical composition of H-bentonite, the charge distribution in unit cell structure, and the formula of the mineral (assumed to be composed of montmorillonite alone) are given below :

Analysis of acid bentonite: SiO_2 , 52.40; Al_2O_3 , 20.20; Fe_2O_3 , 4.5; TiO_2 , 0.20; MgO , 2.80; Na_2O , 0.20; K_2O , 0.10; H_2O , 19.50%; H^+ , 78 me; SiO_2/Al_2O_3 , 4.36.

Charge distribution in component layers of unit cell structure of H-clay: tetrahedral (Si, Al), -1.58; octahedral (Al, Fe^{II} , Mg), 0.72; non-exchangeable cation, 0.07; net unbalanced, -0.79; exchangeable H^+ , 0.70.

Structural formula of clay mineral in clay fraction of bentonite: $[(Si_{7.82} Al_{0.88}) (Al_{2.12} Fe^{III}_{0.42} Ti_{0.02} Mg_{0.10}) (Na_{0.05} K_{0.02})]^{-0.79} H^{+0.70}$.

The titration curves in Fig. 1 reveal that fresh H-bentonite is dibasic in nature, showing two inflections at pH 6.25 and 8.6, and two breaks

Fig. 1. me of NaOH per 100 g of clay.

TABLE 1—X-RAY POWDER DIFFRACTION DATA

H-bent-nite		Aged H-bentonite		Al-gel treated bentonite		Glycerol treated H-bentonite		Glycerol treated aged H-bentonite		Glycerol treated Al-gel-interacted bentonite	
d	I	d	I	d	I	d	I	d	I	d	I
13.88	s	15.06	m(bd)	15.36	bd	18.06	ms	17.85	ms	17.16	ms
10.08	w	9.98	w	9.90	vvw	10.10	w	9.77	vvw	9.81	vw
7.02	vs	7.06	ms	7.01	w	7.10	ms	7.07	s	7.10	ms
4.65	s	4.58	vw	4.55	mw	4.53	w	4.45	w	4.33	vw
3.56	vw	3.56	w	3.66	vvw	3.60	vw	3.60	vw	3.68	w
2.50	mw	2.50	w	2.45	vvw	—	—	—	—	—	—

d = interplaner spacing (Å), I = relative intensity.

vvs = very very strong, vs = very strong, s = strong, ms = medium strong, m = medium, mw = medium weak, w = weak, vw = very weak, vvw = very very weak, bd = broad diffuse.

in conductance at 0.7 and 3.5 μ mho. The corresponding acidities are due to 57 me H₃O⁺ and 22 me Al(H₂O)₆³⁺ per 100 g H-clay. The aged clay sol (4 weeks), in contrast, gives three inflections and breaks in potentiometric and conductometric titration curves, respectively. The inflections at pH 5.2 and 7.0 are due to neutralisation

of 23 me H₃O⁺ and 35 me Al(H₂O)₆³⁺, respectively. The inflection at 8.6 is due to neutralisation of polymeric hydroxy-Al (latent acidity) on aging for 4 weeks.

H-bentonite loses 35 me H₃O⁺ ions which migrate from exchange sites to the edges where they attack

Fig 2 Temperature (°C)

Si-O-Al bonds, resulting in 35 me $\text{Al}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}$ and 21 me polymeric hydroxy-Al.

The titration curve of the mixture of H-clay and aluminium hydroxide gel shows only one inflection and one break in pH and conductance curves, respectively. The neutralisable acidity is equivalent to 70 me/100 g mixture. The absence of H_3O^+ suggests transformation of all such ions into hydroxy-aluminium ions in presence of aluminium hydroxide gel. The monotonous rise of conductance on titration points to a similar conclusion. The total alkali need to titrate fresh H-bentonite and aged bentonite is 79 me but for Al-gel and bentonite mixture it is 75 me/100 g mixture. Thus a decrease

of 4 me/100 g is due to fixation of hydroxy-Al on exchange sites.

Differential thermal curves for fresh and aged bentonite, and for aluminium hydroxide gel-bentonite mixture are given in Fig. 2, which show endothermic dehydration peaks at 150, 135, and 130°, respectively for hygroscopic moisture and interlayer water loss. The endothermic dehydroxylation peak temperature for fresh bentonite at 570° is similarly lowered to 555° in the case of aged bentonite and gel-bentonite mixture. Such lowering in mixed system is known⁵.

The mineralogical characteristics of H-bentonite alter both on aging and on interaction with synthetic gel. The X-ray diffraction diagram show that the basal spacing 13.88 Å of H-bentonite shifts to 15.06 Å (diffuse band) for aged bentonite and to 15.36 Å (diffuse band) for gel-bentonite mixture (Table 1). This indicates that coating with hydroxy-aluminium polymers interferes in the X-ray diffraction pattern⁶. On the other hand, in glycerol treated H-bentonite the basal spacing increases to 18.06 Å, whereas it is 17.85 Å for aged bentonite and 17.16 Å for gel-bentonite mixture. A weak line at about 10 Å in H-bentonite may be due to a small quantity of biotite

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